

PRINCIPLES OF PREPARING STUDENTS OF THE PREPARATORY GROUP IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS FOR SCHOOL

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Annotation. The article focused on what should be considered primarily in preparing children for school before they go to school, and on the principles that children rely on to read their speech, and the laws of reading their perception. Also, on the basis of the stated principles, the opportunities for the gradual development of children's wealth to communicate them are revealed.

Keywords: preschool educational organization, speech, school preparation, preparatory groups, didactic principles, emotional sensitivity, perception.

Going to school is a huge event in the lives of children. School life reveals to children a new world, during the school period the main activities of children change. The more attention is paid to the physical growth of children in kindergarten, the more attention is paid to their mental and moral growth. Their school performances are always intended, and in the various didactic celebrities held, children's perceptions, imagination and memories, fantasies and thoughts, will be systematically developed.

Growing their speech in preparing children for the reading process at school is one of the very necessary conditions. Therefore, when preparing children in the preparatory group for school studies, it is necessary to give ahamiyat that they learn their native languages well, that is, gain vocabulary, be able to correctly pronounce and complete, and make the right sentence. Expanding children's perception of the external world, enrichment work should be carried out on the basis of which they grow their speech. At this age, children develop some concepts of space (long, close, right, left, big, small), concepts of round and Circle, an idea of time (time, today, early, indin, now), and also concepts of morality (good, bad, True, False, ashamed).

When growing children's speech, it is necessary not only to perceive what they see, but also to take into account the existing level of their ability to listen to their interlocutors. When forming children's speech through the development of sensitivity in training, it is required to accurately, fully convey the names of

various items, their characteristics, form a clear picture of the colors, shapes, size of objects. From experience it is known that a child has the property of remembering meaningful concepts, somewhat quickly and firmly, rather than meaningless words. His speech will be enough to engage in communication with adults at the stage of preparation for school education, to read the opinion of people and at the level of correct perception, and the structure of speech, corresponding to the rules of grammar, logically consistent, expressive, quantitatively and across the spectrum, to exchange ideas. He can understand information about what he has heard and seen. He is able to state the information contained in a certain order, makes appropriate use of operations of mental activity (compares them, clarifies them, generalizes them, tries to make judgments and conclusions).

Pedagogical-psychological observations show that further strengthening of sensitivity in children of preschool age when growing speech expands the possibilities of mental development. The initial stage of pedagogical actions aimed at increasing sensitivity in children is the goal of forming concepts based on emotional experience, that is, the environment that surrounds us, entering into interpersonal relationships, understanding specific aspects of social life, being able to think independently, among children of preschool age.

As the child grows older, his influence on the objects around him, his understanding of objects, his imagination, his skills to accept the opinions of others improve. In this regard, the stage of growing up gives an effective result in further psychological development and general understanding. The younger the child, the greater the level of feeling and entering into a relationship will also be of such great importance in his life. In the process of educating emotional sensitivity, it is necessary to give children an understanding of their name, forms, size, color in order to form a skill to distinguish different items from each other. Many educators and psychologists, including L.Wenger, W.According to Mukhina, the formation of emotional sensitivity in children is a process for them to understand the world that surrounds them with the help of emotions, as well as to expand the possibilities of speech and thinking on this basis. Educators should pay special attention to this in the pre-school activities.

In preschool children, there are a number of laws regarding the essence of perception and its development.

Including:

1. Perception and perception are not viewed as receptor processes, but as reflector processes, in which perception and perception are not a complete

manifestation of an object, their qualities are clearly expressed, but a special specific action of analyzers aimed at capturing the properties of things. The development of perception, on the other hand, is a continuous process aimed at the child's acquisition of sensory-based movements.

2. The development of perception in children means the assimilation of social emotional experience. In such conditions, while the emotional ability in a child is poorly developed, with the help of parents and caregivers, a perceptual observation process is manifested, which is primarily considered a means of knowing the child's environment for the emergence of such an ability. Perceptual observation refers to the abilities of a person's team members, pedagogical staff, as well as students to be able to enter the inner world, psychological observation, perception of the subtleties of subordinates associated with temporary psychic States. Only then does the system of étalones apply. As a result, the child learns to use them. In turn, they serve as a criterion for assessing children's emotional experiences. They manage to intensively master the norms of geometric shapes, colors, volumes of objects and objects, low - height materials, sounds, expression of ideas, communication and interaction.

The preschool education system is set the following tasks before the process of growing children's speech and preparing them for interaction:

- formation of a system of perceptual actions in children;
- the system of emotional sensitivity Etalons in children – to form generalized perceptions of the names, properties, mutually differing aspects of things and objects, their relationship to the environment;
- formation of skills of independent execution of perceptual actions in children;
- teaching children to use the system of Etalons in perception and practical activities.

The content of the educational process, which is carried out for the purpose of preparing children for school, includes the names of objects and objects that should be understood by children, features and qualities of phenomena. They are determined by the color, originality of the environment according to their characteristics and types of activities. It is important that the objects are designed to move by sight, capture, or by looking at their shapes with their eyes depending on their sound. This in turn requires independent thinking from children, careful attitude towards their activities, observation. As a result of this, moral qualities are formed in the child. Tevarak-cognitive activity is formed in

children by the fact that phenomena happening around, for example, the names, shapes, large-small size, structure, color separation of things-objects. The child learns their names in the process of getting acquainted with things-objects, natural phenomena, the world of animals and plants. These are of particular importance in the development of a child's speech. Children see and perceive the names, volumes, colors, shapes and spatial States of things.

In conclusion, we can say that the readiness of children for school, psychologically, is an important foundation for the education and maturation of the individual. The goal set for the educational process is achieved only if our pedagogical psychologists comprehensively develop children from the psychological, physiological, physical side to the mental preparation for school.

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